

KEEPERS

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Annotation. The holder is a switching electrical apparatus that separates the protective circuit from the M Anba using a special element.

Summary: the holder is a switching electrical apparatus that separates the protective circuit from the source using a special element.

Keywords: Noble conservative, soluble preservative, quartz sand, short circuit current, nominal current, disconnect current

The most valuable feature of Meltdown Keepers is the extreme simplicity of the device, low cost, very fast chain disconnection at short circuit current (even limiting the short circuit current of some keepers), and others. Soluble inclusions are made of lead and its alloys or thin copper wire. The holders are non-separable and detachable and are marked with PN and PR respectively. In an NPN-type holder, quartz sand is filled, which serves to extinguish the arc faster when the sand deposit melts. It is based on the fact that when the EYUK value exceeds a certain amount in an excellent current leads to the melting of the conductor and disconnecting the chain. The arc produced during the simultaneous discontinuity is also quenched. The holder is considered the simplest apparatus of Electrotechnics and serves to protect the electrical device from overloading and short circuit current. Small voltage m die holders can be produced from milliamper to thousands of am per, and voltage up to 600 V, high voltage m die holders up to 35 kV and above. Their melting element is characterized by nominal current and voltage, the nominal current of the holder, the marginal value of the disconnecting current, etc. The nominal current of the holder is said to be the current passing through its current conductor and contact devices. The nominal current of the melting element is the current that does not lead to the melting of the element until it is reached, long past the melting element. The marginal value of the break current is said to be the QT current that disconnects the holder without damaging its parts. Small voltage m die holders can be produced from milliamper to thousands of am per, and voltage up to 600 V, high voltage m die holders up to 35 kV and above. Their melting element is characterized by nominal current and voltage, the nominal current of the holder, the marginal value of the disconnecting current, etc. The nominal current of the holder is said to be the current passing through its current

conductor and contact devices. The nominal current of the melting element is the current that does not carry the element until it is reached, passing for a long time from the melting element. The break current is said to be a marginal torture at a QT current that disconnects the holder without damaging its parts. When the wire is 25÷30% more than the nominal, the storage element burns for 1÷2 hours, when the wire is 50% more than the nominal it should burn for 10÷15, and when it is 100% more, it should burn within 1 minute. To increase the speed of operation of the holders, soluble elements made of various materials and of a special shape are used. Copper, zinc, aluminum, lead and silver are used in the preparation of soluble elements.

PK type storage:

A is its structure; B is its vertical installation;
 volt-second description of the D-holder.

In PK - type storage devices, the melting of the solute begins to melt long before it reaches the specified (ustanovochny) current, and when the current reaches the measurement value, that is, it breaks the chain before it reaches the maximum value of the sinusoid and the transition from the zero value (figure d).

References:

1. Elektr tarmoqlari va sistemalari: uslubiy qo'llanma/ O'zR OO'MTV; Rasulov A.N., Taslimov A.D., Mamarasulova F.S., Raxmonov I.U.-Toshkent: TDTU, 2014. - 90 b.
2. Xoshimov F.A., Taslimov A.D. Energiya tejamlorligi asoslari. O'quv qo'llanma. -T. : Voris, 2014.
3. Karimov X.G., Bobojonov M.Q. Avtomatik boshqarish va rostlash nazariyasi asoslari. O'quv qo'llanma. - T.: Intellekt ekspert, 2014.
4. Statistics have been drawn from BP Statistical Review of World Energy, June 2003,
5. International Energy Outlook, March 2002, Energy Information administration, Office of
6. ENERGY FACT BOOK 2022-2023 Canada

7. Secondary Energy Infobook 2019-2020
8. O.O. Hoshimov, A.T. Imomnazarov. Elektr mexanik tizimlarda energiya tejamkorligi: Toshkent — 2015
9. Yuldashev, H. T., & Mirzaev, S. Z. (2021). Investigation of background radiation and the possibility of its limitation in a semiconductor ionization system. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(4), 1364-1369. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=F0CurZQAAAAJ&citation_for_view=F0CurZQAAAAJ:YsMSGlbcyi4C
10. Саматов, Н. А., Эргашев, М. М., & Хасанов, Г. Х. (2018). Эффективные технологии использования возобновляемых источников энергии в жилых зданиях. In современная наука: проблемы и перспективы (pp. 8-10).
11. Nurali, P., Javlonbek, X., & Xolmirza, M. (2023). O'zgarmas tok dvigatelining quvvat isrofi va uning foydali ish koeffitsiyentiga ta'sir. *Innovations in Technology and Science Education*, 2(9), 120-127. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=EnEF7YEAAAAJ&citation_for_view=EnEF7YEAAAAJ:zYLM7Y9cAGgC

